

1 **Risk factors and geospatial associations with *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria infection and IgG**
2 **seroprevalence: Nigeria, 2018**

3 **Running Title:** *P. falciparum* risk factors in Nigeria

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23 **Article summary:** Serological tools provide more nuanced information beyond rapid diagnostic tests and
24 microscopy on exposure history to *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria; geospatial analysis augments
25 examination of spatial heterogeneities in malaria transmission. This study leveraged both approaches to
26 assess malaria burden across Nigeria.

27 **Abstract**

28 **Background.** Nigeria consistently shows the greatest population burden of *Plasmodium falciparum* (Pf)
29 malaria. While rapid diagnostic tests and microscopy offer valuable information for clinical decisions and
30 prevalence estimates, serological tools provide more nuanced information on exposure history to Pf,
31 enhancing the ability to assess and track malaria burden at a population level.

32 **Methods.** Blood samples (n=89,438) from a nationwide 2018 HIV household survey in Nigeria were
33 assayed for active/recent infection by testing for the Pf HRP2 and LDH antigens, and for Pf exposure by
34 immunoglobulin G carriage against a panel of antigens. Risk factors for Pf infection and exposure were
35 assessed using logistic regression and geospatial analyses.

36 **Results.** By blood antigenemia, current/recent Pf prevalence was 38.3% (95% CI: 37.2–39.5%), and
37 seroprevalence among the panel of five Pf antigens ranged from 48% to 87%. In multivariate regression
38 models, participants age 5–14 years had the highest odds of active infection versus children <5 years.
39 Compared to the lowest wealth category, the wealthiest category showed a 5-fold reduction in odds of
40 active infection, and urban living was associated with a 30% reduction. In estimating a longer window of
41 Pf exposure, serology recapitulated these associations with [LS2.1][AJ2.2]the highest wealth category
42 showing a 10-fold reduction, and urban living a 60% reduction, in exposure.

43 **Conclusions.** Geospatial findings underscored Nigeria’s hyperendemic but heterogeneous malaria
44 epidemiology with infection and exposure are not unequally distributed among the populace. Serological
45 data can provide greater insights into malaria risk factor analyses and augment examination of spatial
46 heterogeneities in transmission.

47

48 **Key words:** seroprevalence, malaria risk factors, *Plasmodium falciparum*, geospatial associations

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53 **Background**

54 Nigeria has consistently shown the highest burden of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria in the
55 world, accounting for approximately 26% of all global malaria cases and 31% of deaths in 2023.¹ Though
56 prevention efforts between 2010 and 2015 led to a substantial decrease in malaria prevalence², there have
57 been no significant changes in the malaria mortality rate for nearly a decade¹. Malaria diagnosis at health
58 facilities in Nigeria primarily uses rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) that detect the histidine-rich protein 2
59 (HRP2) antigen expressed exclusively by *P. falciparum*¹; these HRP2-based RDTs were also used during
60 the most recent Demographic and Health Survey (DHS, in 2018), as well as the most recent Malaria
61 Indicator Survey (MIS, in 2021).³ An estimated 36.2% of children aged 6–59 months in 2018—and
62 39.6% in 2021—had active *P. falciparum* infection at time of survey.³

63 Though HRP2-based RDTs are the most common method for assessing malaria burden in
64 Nigeria, additional information can be gained from detection of *Plasmodium* lactate dehydrogenase
65 (LDH) antigen as well as detection of immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies against a range of *P.*
66 *falciparum* antigens expressed during the parasite life cycle. Blood concentration of the LDH antigen
67 correlates well with blood-stage parasite density⁴ and thus provides important supplementary information
68 about the level of host *P. falciparum* burden beyond just its presence. IgG antibodies against *P.*
69 *falciparum* antigens provide further nuance due to their persistence after infection, indicating cumulative
70 exposure to these parasites and serving as a proxy measure for population-level transmission intensity.⁵
71 Well-characterized antigens that elicit short-term B-cell responses during a range of life cycle stages in
72 the human host include those in the sporozoite (e.g., circumsporozoite surface protein, CSP), liver (e.g.,
73 liver-stage antigen 1, LSA1), and merozoite (e.g., glutamate-rich protein, GLURP) stages. While these
74 targets can provide information on an individual's recent *P. falciparum* exposure, more-immunogenic
75 antigens produced during blood-stage infection, such as apical membrane antigen 1 (AMA1) and
76 merozoite surface protein 1 (MSP1), are associated with longer-term IgG responses remaining up to
77 decades after exposure.^{6,7}

78 Various factors have been consistently found to be associated with *P. falciparum* infection,
79 including age⁸, socioeconomic status⁹, population density¹⁰, and altitude¹¹. By leveraging serological data,
80 this current study examines risk factors and geospatial variables associated with *P. falciparum* infection,
81 estimated parasite density, and previous *P. falciparum* exposure using blood samples collected at
82 households during the 2018 nationwide Nigeria HIV/AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey (NAIIS). In the
83 context of previous examinations of the 2018 NAIIS^{12,13}, this study aims to provide a comprehensive,
84 nationwide analysis of *P. falciparum* risk factors in Nigeria among individuals of all ages, as well as a
85 fine-scale spatial analysis among children <15 years of age.

86

87 **Methods**

88 *Ethics and consent*

89 Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the NAIIS. Parents or guardians granted
90 consent for biomarker testing and future testing on behalf of their children ≤ 17 years of age; children ages
91 10–17 years also provided assent. The National Health Research Ethics Committee of Nigeria
92 (NHREC/01/01/2007) approved secondary laboratory testing of malaria biomarkers as part of the Nigeria
93 Multi-disease Serologic Surveillance using Stored Specimens (NMS4) project. The U.S. Centers for
94 Disease Control and Prevention Human Subjects Office determined that testing did not constitute human
95 subjects research (project 0900f3eb819d4c63).

96

97 *Survey design*

98 As previously reported, the NAIIS 2018 was a national HIV population-based household survey
99 conducted by the Government of Nigeria under the purview of the Federal Ministry of Health.¹⁴ Briefly, a
100 stratified two-stage cluster sampling design was used with 37 strata comprising 36 states and the Federal
101 Capital Territory. Enumeration areas (EAs) were selected within each stratum using probabilities
102 proportional to their estimated population size. A simple random sample of households was taken for each
103 EA chosen for survey inclusion. All usual residents ages 15 to 64 years of selected households were

104 eligible to participate, and one-quarter of households were randomly sampled to include children 0 to 14
105 years old. Venous blood (capillary collection for children aged <2 years) was collected from consenting
106 participants, transported to designated satellite laboratories for processing into plasma and dried blood
107 spots (DBS), and frozen within 24 hours of blood collection before being transported to the National
108 Reference Laboratory (NRL) in Abuja.

109 *Plasmodium* antigen and antibody data were collected on NAIIS samples through the Nigeria Multi-
110 disease Serologic Surveillance using Stored Specimens (NMS4) project. For this current study, results
111 from specimens for all participants under 15 years of age and a subset from women of reproductive age,
112 as well as from all participants under age 65 residing in the 11 Nigerian states supported by the U.S.
113 President's Malaria Initiative were included.¹⁵

114

115 *Multiplex laboratory assays for detection of parasite antigen and human IgG responses*

116 The NRL laboratory processed all biospecimens for detection of the *P. falciparum* antigens HRP2
117 and LDH, and human IgG responses to the *P. falciparum* antigens MSP-1-19kd, AMA1, CSP, LSA-1,
118 GLURP0, and the assay control antigen GST. These multiplex antibody detection¹⁶ and antigen
119 detection¹⁷ assays have been described previously, and further details are provided in Supplemental
120 Methods.

121

122 *Statistical analysis*

123 Statistical analysis was similar to that conducted for previous estimates of non-*P. falciparum*
124 malaria in Nigeria.¹³ Survey questionnaire data were cleaned using Census and Survey Processing System
125 (CSPro) version 7.7.2 (U.S. Census Bureau; census.gov/data/software/cspro) and SAS version 9.4 (SAS
126 Institute, Cary, NC). DBS with GST MFI-bg reads above 500 were excluded from IgG analysis due to
127 evidence for non-specific IgG binding. The assay signal threshold for antigen and antibody positivity was
128 determined using a finite mixture model approach, which estimated the “antigen-negative” population
129 within these data and established a cutoff using the mean plus two standard deviations.¹⁹ Finite mixture

130 models were run separately for the initial tranche of specimens (children <15 years of age and a sample of
131 women of reproductive age) and the second tranche (individuals ≥ 15 years of age in 11 states), given that
132 they used different batches of reagents. Malaria outcomes were analyzed in SAS with adjustments made
133 for the complex survey design of the NAIIS. Data were weighted using normalized survey weights. For
134 the risk factor analysis, demographic, socioeconomic, and behavioral risk factors were assessed for their
135 relationship with HRP2, PfLDH, and IgG outcomes using logistic regression models. The insecticide-
136 treated net (ITN) access variable was a binary household-level variable derived using World Health
137 Organization (WHO) criteria for universal net coverage of at least one ITN per 1.8 household members,
138 since NAIIS ITN data were not collected for individual participants.²⁰ As PfLDH concentrations track
139 closely with *P. falciparum* parasite density, the PfLDH outcome was assessed for both a positive versus
140 negative response with binomial logistic regression, and for moderate and high positive responses versus
141 low using a multinomial (generalized logit) regression, to examine associations with increased *P.*
142 *falciparum* parasite density at time of sampling.²¹ Low, moderate, and high positive responses were based
143 on log-tertiles of estimated PfLDH concentration. An alpha level of 0.001 indicated statistical
144 significance.

145 Serocatalytic conversion models were fit to seropositivity by age data for each antigen using
146 standard maximum likelihood and assuming a binomial error distribution. These models were used to
147 estimate the seroconversion rate (SCR) by incorporating the mean annual rate of conversion to
148 seropositive and the mean annual rate of reversion from seropositive to seronegative for all *P. falciparum*
149 antibodies analyzed.^{5,22} This was performed for all participants (<65 years of age) and separately for
150 children <15 years. In both cases, participants <1 year were excluded to remove effects of maternally
151 derived anti-malarial IgG antibodies. Models were fit in R (version 4.2.0; R Foundation for Statistical
152 Computing, Vienna, Austria).

153

154 *Spatial analysis*

155 Geospatial analysis of seroprevalence to short-term antigens CSP, GLURP0, and LSA1 and
156 prevalence to HRP2 was conducted at the local government area (LGA) level among children <15 years
157 of age, as they were the only group included in all LGAs surveyed (**Fig. S1**). Analysis was performed
158 using R-INLA in R version 4.2.0.²³ Independent variables with known or putative relationships with
159 malaria infection and exposure in previous spatial models of malaria²⁴⁻²⁶ were included in the models,
160 including altitude, aridity, population density, rainfall, air temperature, and travel time to the nearest
161 urban center. Remote sensing data were obtained from outside sources and averaged for each LGA using
162 QGIS version 3.20.3-Odense (**Table S1**). Because malaria prevalence varies by age, the average age of
163 children surveyed in each LGA was also incorporated (**Table S2**). An alpha level of 0.05 indicated
164 statistical significance.

165 Results were extracted as mean estimated beta coefficients with 95% credible intervals and as
166 LGA-specific (sero)prevalence estimates. The latter was used to compare results among each outcome
167 (HRP2 antigen, CSP IgG, GLURP0 IgG, and LSA1 IgG) using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.
168 Exceedance probabilities (i.e., the probability that a given LGA would exceed a predetermined threshold
169 of (sero)prevalence) indicated unusual elevations of risk. Thresholds were based on median
170 (sero)prevalence values for all LGAs (**Table S3**). Mean (sero)prevalence and exceedance probabilities
171 were visualized using QGIS.

172

173 **Results**

174 *Demographic characteristics*

175 In total, 88,854 DBS samples were assessed for persons <65 years of age (**Table 1**), after
176 excluding 584 DBS (0.65% of the original 89,438) with MFI-bg reads >500 for the GST internal assay
177 control. Most participants (66.2%, 95% CI: 63.9–68.6%) lived in a rural area and a majority were female
178 (53.6%, 95% CI: 52.4–54.7%). Most households (81.8%, 95% CI: 80.1–83.5%) did not have adequate
179 ownership of bed nets (i.e., at least 1 ITN per 1.8 household members). Prevalence of *P. falciparum*
180 infection at time of sampling was 38.3% (95% CI: 37.2–39.5%) based on a positive HRP2 signal, and

181 34.5% (95% CI: 33.4–35.6%) of participants had a positive signal to PfLDH. Estimated seroprevalence to
182 long-term *P. falciparum* exposure markers AMA1 and MSP1 was 85.0% (95% CI: 83.4–86.6%) and
183 86.9% (95% CI: 85.3–88.4%), respectively, while estimated seroprevalence to GLURP0 (53.5%, 95% CI:
184 52.4–54.7%) was the highest among short-term exposure markers, followed by CSP (48.7%, 95% CI:
185 47.5–49.9%) and LSA1 (40.0%, 95% CI: 39.1–40.9%). IgG levels among short-term antigen markers
186 correlated well (**Fig. S2**).

187

188 *Seroconversion rates*

189 For persons <65 years of age, the estimated mean annual conversion rate from seronegative to
190 seropositive was significantly different among markers of short-term exposure. The estimated SCR was
191 lowest for CSP (0.049, 95% CI: 0.048–0.050), followed by LSA1 (0.063, 95% CI: 0.061–0.064) and
192 GLURP0 (0.076, 95% CI: 0.074–0.077) (**Figure 1**). Among the long-term antigen markers, the SCR for
193 MSP1 was 0.37 (95% CI: 0.36–0.38), which was significantly higher than for AMA1 (0.22, 95% CI:
194 0.21–0.22). When modeled using only data from children <15 years of age, the SCR was also low for
195 CSP (0.055, 95% CI: 0.051–0.058) relative to the rates of seroconversion for GLURP0 (0.072, 95% CI:
196 0.069–0.076) and LSA1 (0.078, 95% CI: 0.072–0.083) (**Fig. S3**), and the SCR for MSP1 (0.71, 95% CI:
197 0.67–0.75) was significantly higher than for AMA1 (0.40, 95% CI: 0.38–0.42). Regardless of age group,
198 estimated SCR for all antigens was successively lower for each relative increase in household wealth
199 (**Figure 2A, Fig. S4**). Estimated SCRs of persons living in an urban residence were significantly lower
200 than SCRs of those living in a rural residence, also regardless of age grouping (**Figure 2B, Fig. S5**). The
201 effect of wealth on seroconversion was salient even when examining rural and urban households
202 separately (**Fig. S6**).

203

204 *Risk factor analysis for persons <65 years*

205 Male participants had higher odds of positive HRP2 (adjusted OR: 1.3, 95% CI: 1.2–1.3) and
206 PfLDH (adjusted OR: 1.2, 95% CI: 1.2–1.3) compared to female participants. Compared to children <5

207 years of age, participants aged 5–14 years had the highest odds of *P. falciparum* infection while older age
208 groups (15–64 years) had significantly lower odds of infection (**Table 2, Table S4**). Older persons also
209 had lower odds of overall PfLDH positivity and, when infected, lower odds of higher density Pf
210 infections than the youngest age group. Age had a dose-response relationship with IgG seropositivity to
211 each of the *P. falciparum* antigens, with older groups having successively higher odds of exposure than
212 children <5 years (**Table 3, Table S5**). Compared to the poorest quintile, residence in a wealthier
213 household was protective against *P. falciparum* infection and exposure. The highest wealth quintile was
214 associated with an 80% (95% CI: 0.2–0.2) reduction in odds of *P. falciparum* infection by both the HRP2
215 and PfLDH targets (**Table 2**) and between a 40 and 60% reduction of odds in seropositivity to the five
216 different IgG targets (**Table 3**) compared to the poorest. Residing in an urban setting was associated with
217 a 30% reduction in the odds of *P. falciparum* infection (95% CI: 0.6–0.7), and significantly lower odds of
218 seropositivity to all *P. falciparum* antigens ranging from 30% to 60% (**Table 2, Table 3**). While having
219 adequate access to ITNs (i.e., at least one ITN per 1.8 household members) had a null effect against active
220 *P. falciparum* infection, the odds of seropositivity to most *P. falciparum* antigens were significantly
221 higher among participants in households with such access versus those without.

222

223 *Geospatial analysis among children <15 years*

224 Among children <15 years, local government areas (LGAs) with elevated risk of seroprevalence
225 to short-term *P. falciparum* exposure markers were reflective of LGAs with higher risk of HRP2
226 prevalence (**Figure 3**). As prevalence of HRP2 antigenemia was higher than PfLDH (38.3% vs 34.5%,
227 **Table 1**), we only considered HRP2 as a marker of Pf infection in this analysis. This was mirrored in
228 maps visualizing levels of (sero)prevalence by LGA (**Fig. S7**). Variables assessed in geospatial models
229 had similar relationships with *P. falciparum* infection (HRP2 positivity) and short-term *P. falciparum*
230 exposure (CSP, LSA1, GLURP0 IgG positivity) in terms of direction (**Figure 4, Table S6**). The only
231 variable with statistically significant relationships for all outcomes was population density, whereby
232 higher population density (i.e., a more urban setting) was associated with lower odds of *P. falciparum*

233 infection and exposure. Mean age by LGA was associated with higher odds of *P. falciparum* exposure.
234 Increased travel time to the nearest urban center, increased aridity, and increased temperature were
235 associated with higher odds of *P. falciparum* infection and exposure. Increased rainfall and altitude were
236 associated with lower odds of *P. falciparum* infection and exposure. Correlation was strongest between
237 HRP2 prevalence and CSP seroprevalence ($\rho = 0.70$, 95% CI: 0.66–0.74). Spearman’s rank correlation
238 coefficients for internal comparisons of seroprevalence estimates among the three short-term antigens
239 were strong (**Table S7**).

240

241 **Discussion**

242 This study investigated associations of key sociodemographic and environmental variables with
243 infection and previous exposure to *P. falciparum* malaria among persons aged <65 years from the
244 Nigerian NAHS 2018 household survey. Active or recent infection was indicated by a positive HRP2
245 signal from a sensitive laboratory assay rather than a point-of-contact RDT result, and previous exposure
246 determined by IgG seroprevalence to malaria antigen markers, serving as a separate but complementary
247 metric of malaria transmission. Serological data has previously been used to complement malaria
248 prevalence estimates with examples from entomological approaches such as annual parasite index²⁷ and
249 clinical diagnostic methods including microscopy, rapid diagnostic tests, and polymerase chain reaction²⁸.
250 Malaria serology has also yielded complementary spatial estimates highlighting geographic areas of high
251 malaria exposure.²⁹

252 Utilizing *P. falciparum* data generated from laboratory assays, risk factor analysis of the 2018
253 NAHS shows that males had higher odds of active infection compared to females. Higher malaria
254 prevalence in males has been reported in both hypoendemic and hyperendemic settings among both
255 school-aged and adult participants³⁰⁻³². A recent study conducted in Uganda pointed to biological sex-
256 based differences that accounted for male bias, positing that females cleared asymptomatic infections at a
257 faster rate than males in the absence of other possible explanations, such as behavioral trends³³. Further
258 investigation on the interplay between host sex and malaria infection is needed, particularly potential

259 differences in immune response between males and females, as estrogen may play a role in modulating
260 this response³⁴.

261 Persons ages 5–14 years had significantly higher risk of active *P. falciparum* infection compared
262 to children under 5 years. When older persons (>15 years) were found to be infected with *P. falciparum*,
263 they harbored lower parasite densities compared to young, infected persons, and this is likely due to
264 acquired anti-parasite immunity. This finding of higher parasite prevalence in school-age children
265 compared to the very young and adults residing in the same area has been found in other studies.
266 Compared to younger children, Malawian children ages 6–15 years were found to be at highest risk of
267 infection³⁵ and infection risk was highest among 5–9-year-olds in Uganda³⁶. It is possible that school-age
268 children acquire *P. falciparum* infections at the same rate as younger children but harbor them for longer
269 without progressing to severe disease likely due to some acquired immunity.³⁷

270 One of the strongest associations found in these data showed that increases in a household’s
271 wealth were associated with lower risk of malaria in a dose-response fashion, with an 80% reduction in
272 odds of *P. falciparum* infection—and up to a 90% reduction in odds of exposure (to AMA1)—for the
273 highest quintile versus the lowest. Previous findings point to this relationship, summarized in a recent
274 meta-analysis of *P. falciparum* infection in sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁰ These results also corroborate results
275 from a non-falciparum risk factor analysis of this same NMS4 dataset¹³. Wealth is a complex factor, as
276 improved housing structures, improved access to health care, and better nutrition are afforded with
277 increased wealth—and each of these components are themselves protective against mosquito exposure
278 and subsequent parasite exposure. Similarly, living in an urban residence had a significantly protective
279 effect on malaria infection and exposure, and this association was observed essentially from birth. This
280 finding has also been corroborated by previous studies summarized by Doumbe-Belisse *et al.*; among
281 other factors, pollution in the environment as well as greater mosquito avoidance among urban dwellers
282 foster sub-optimal vector conditions, contributing to lower *P. falciparum* exposure risk.³⁸

283 In this cross-sectional study, adequate access to bed nets in a household was associated with
284 moderate reductions in odds of HRP2 and PfLDH positivity, but also small increases in odds of

285 seropositivity to antigens indicating short- (GLURP0, LSA1, CSP) and long-term (AMA1, MSP1) history
286 of exposure. Because rates of bed net ownership often exceed those of actual usage³⁹, it is important to
287 collect additional data related to the determinants of ITN usage, such as sleeping arrangements and
288 perceived risk of malaria infection⁴⁰. A qualitative analysis examined findings of higher malaria
289 prevalence among diligent users of bed nets, pointing to previous infection as a major impetus for
290 increased ITN use⁴¹. ITNs may thus reduce infections among those who have already been exposed to
291 malaria, offering a potential explanation for this study's finding.

292 Spatial analysis findings supported those from the risk factor analysis. As travel time to an urban
293 center increased (i.e., as an area became more rural), odds of *P. falciparum* infection or exposure
294 increased; likewise, as population density increased (i.e., as a location became more urban), these odds
295 decreased. Increased average age of participants was similarly associated with increased odds of
296 seropositivity to *P. falciparum* antigens. Along with altitude, associations with non-temporal factors have
297 been found by other groups in a range of endemic settings^{10,11,24-26,42,43}. However, observed associations
298 with aridity, rainfall, and temperature depend on survey timing, which could not be accounted for in this
299 study; for example, though the wet season is generally marked by increased malaria incidence, heavy
300 rainfall may wash away mosquito breeding sites, reducing vector exposure^{44,45}.

301 There were several limitations of this study. As indicated above, because of the single time point
302 of this cross-sectional survey, it was not possible to assess temporality or effects of seasonality on malaria
303 outcomes, particularly carriage of HRP2 and PfLDH. The household sampling design was more likely to
304 capture people with mild or asymptomatic malaria (i.e., persons not seeking medical care), limiting
305 assessment of symptoms. The design may have also limited the ability to detect transmission hotspots due
306 to smoothing of localized variation. Though sampling design was based on the most recent Nigerian
307 census data, the goal of the survey was generating state-level point estimates for HIV; malaria-specific
308 data, including confounders such as symptoms and individual bed net use, were not collected. Statistical
309 analyses were based on data from 11 of 36 Nigerian states, limiting generalizability of results; similarly,
310 geospatial results were limited to participants <15 years and may not be generalizable to other age groups.

311 As Nigeria and other countries in sub-Saharan Africa progress toward malaria control and
312 eventual elimination in the future, serology can be an essential complement for epidemiological data that
313 can supplement passive or active case reporting. Risk factors for *P. falciparum* assessed in this
314 nationwide 2018 survey point to similar relationships with both previous exposure and active infection,
315 and serological data can further augment analyses for examining spatial heterogeneities in transmission.
316 This comprehensive, nationwide view of *P. falciparum* burden in Nigeria could serve as a reference point
317 for malaria progress in the country regarding prevalence, spatial heterogeneity, and interventions going
318 forward.

319

320 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

321 Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the NAHS. Parents or guardians granted consent
322 for biomarker testing and future testing on behalf of their children ≤ 17 years of age; children ages 10–17
323 years also provided assent. The National Health Research Ethics Committee of Nigeria
324 (NHREC/01/01/2007) approved secondary laboratory testing of malaria biomarkers as part of the Nigeria
325 Multi-disease Serologic Surveillance using Stored Specimens (NMS4) project. The U.S. Centers for
326 Disease Control and Prevention Human Subjects Office determined that testing did not constitute human
327 subjects research (project 0900f3eb819d4c63).

328

329 **Data availability**

330 DHS data are publicly available for download. NMS4 data are owned by the Government of Nigeria
331 (GoN); requests for NMS4 data must be approved by GoN and all other NMS4 principal investigators.
332 Inquiries should be directed to the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC).

333

334 **Competing Interests**

335 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

336

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342

343 **Author contributions**

344 AJU and ER conceived of the idea for this manuscript; AJU undertook the analyses with contributions
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360

361 **Disclaimer**

362 The findings and conclusions in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the
363 official position of the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, NAIIS group, or Nigeria Centre
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365

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492 **Figure Legends**

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494 **Figure 1. Seropositivity by age for IgG against *P. falciparum* antigens AMA1, CSP, GLURP0,**
495 **LSA1, and MSP1 for persons <65 years: Nigeria, 2018.** Dots indicate the proportion seropositive while
496 error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for seropositivity in each age group. Fits of each catalytic
497 seroconversion model are represented by curves, while shaded areas are 95% credible intervals of model
498 predictions. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95% confidence intervals for IgG
499 against each antigen. All plots represent data from 87,344 biologically independent samples.

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Figure 2. IgG seropositivity by age for *P. falciparum* MSP1, AMA1, CSP, GLURP0, and LSA1 antigens by wealth quintile and urban/rural residence: Nigeria, 2018. Dots indicate the proportion seropositive while error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for each age group. Curves represent the fitting to the catalytic seroconversion model and shaded areas are 95% credible intervals. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95% confidence intervals. All plots represent data from 87,344 biologically independent samples.

Figure 3. Exceedance probabilities for seroprevalence to short-term *P. falciparum* antigen markers and prevalence of active *P. falciparum* infection among children <15 years of age: Nigeria, 2018. Exceedance probabilities indicating elevated risk of (sero)prevalence to (A) CSP IgG, (B) GLURP0 IgG, (C) LSA1 IgG, and (D) HRP2 antigen are depicted for each of 694 local government areas (LGAs) of 774 in Nigeria for which DBS data were collected and available for analysis. Probabilities are calculated based on (sero)prevalence estimates from R-INLA models that adjusted for mean participant age, altitude, aridity, population density, rainfall, temperature, and travel time to the nearest urban center. Darker purple shading indicates higher probability of exceeding the indicated threshold, while white shading indicates uncertainty of exceedance; darker green shading indicates lower probability of exceeding a given threshold. LGAs in grey had no data either collected or available for analysis.

Figure 4. Mean estimated coefficients of covariates with 95% credible intervals for (sero)prevalence to CSP, GLURP0, LSA1, and HRP2 at the local government area level among children <15 years: Nigeria, 2018. All covariates have been mean-centered and standardized. Dots represent mean estimated beta coefficients for covariates used in R-INLA models and bars are the coefficients' 95% credible intervals. A vertical line at 0.0 represents a null effect; bars that do not cross this line indicate the corresponding covariate had a statistically significant effect on seroprevalence to a given target at an alpha level of 0.05.

526 Tables

527

528 Table 1. Demographic characteristics for persons ages <65 years with *P. falciparum* laboratory

529 data: Nigeria, 2018*.

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Variable	Count (=88854) [§]	Percentage	(95% CI)
Sex			
Female	47583	53.6	(52.4, 54.7)
Male	41271	46.4	(45.6, 47.3)
Age group in years			
<5	13920	15.7	(15.1, 16.2)
5–9	15858	17.8	(17.3, 18.4)
10–14	16196	18.2	(17.6, 18.8)
15–29	25527	28.7	(27.9, 29.5)
30–64	17352	19.5	(19.1, 20)
Wealth quintile			
Lowest wealth	20111	22.6	(21.2, 24.1)
Second lowest	20489	23.1	(21.8, 24.3)
Middle	20214	22.8	(21.6, 23.9)
Second highest	15877	17.9	(16.9, 18.8)
Wealthiest	12162	13.7	(12.8, 14.6)
At least 1 ITN per 1.8 household members			
No	72685	81.8	(80.1, 83.5)
Yes	16100	18.1	(17.4, 18.8)
Missing	69	0.1	(0, 0.1)
Place of residence			
Rural	58849	66.2	(63.9, 68.6)
Urban	30005	33.8	(31.7, 35.9)
HRP2 antigen			
Negative	54457	61.3	(60, 62.5)
Positive	34041	38.3	(37.2, 39.5)
Invalid/Missing	357	0.4	(0.3, 0.5)
PfLDH antigen			
Negative	57854	65.1	(63.8, 66.4)
Positive	30647	34.5	(33.4, 35.6)
Low level positive	10214	11.5	(11.1, 11.9)
Moderate level positive	10215	11.5	(11, 12)
High level positive	10218	11.5	(10.9, 12.1)
Invalid/Missing	353	0.4	(0.3, 0.5)
AMA1 antibody			
Negative	12781	14.4	(13.8, 15)
Positive	75529	85.0	(83.4, 86.6)

Invalid/Missing	544	0.6	(0.5, 0.7)
CSP antibody			
Negative	45170	50.8	(49.6, 52.1)
Positive	43254	48.7	(47.5, 49.9)
Invalid/Missing	431	0.5	(0.4, 0.6)
GLURP0 antibody			
Negative	40844	46.0	(44.8, 47.1)
Positive	47558	53.5	(52.4, 54.7)
Invalid/Missing	452	0.5	(0.4, 0.6)
LSA1 antibody			
Negative	52898	59.5	(58.3, 60.7)
Positive	35526	40.0	(39.1, 40.9)
Invalid/Missing	430	0.5	(0.4, 0.6)
MSP1 antibody			
Negative	11066	12.5	(12, 12.9)
Positive	77199	86.9	(85.3, 88.4)
Invalid/Missing	590	0.7	(0.5, 0.8)

531 95% CI: 95% confidence interval

532 *With valid data for HRP2, PflDH, AMA1, CSP, GLURP0, or MSP1.

533 §Observations with GST MFI >500 were excluded for quality assurance.

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536 **Table 2. Adjusted odds ratio estimates for *P. falciparum* infection by HRP2 and by PfLDH and**
 537 **higher *P. falciparum* density by PflDH considering demographic, socioeconomic, and behavioral**
 538 **risk factors: Nigeria, 2018.**

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Variable	HRP2 Adjusted OR (95% CI)	PflDH Adjusted OR (95% CI)		
	Positive vs. Negative	Positive vs. Negative	Moderate Positive vs. Low Positive	High Positive vs. Low Positive
Sex				
Female	ref	ref	ref	ref
Male	1.3 (1.2, 1.3)*	1.2 (1.2, 1.3)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.5 (0.5, 0.6)*
Age group in years				
<5	ref	ref	ref	ref
5–9	1.7 (1.6, 1.8)*	1.7 (1.6, 1.9)*	1.1 (0.9, 1.4)	0.9 (0.8, 1.2)
10–14	1.6 (1.4, 1.7)*	1.5 (1.4, 1.7)*	0.9 (0.7, 1.1)	0.5 (0.4, 0.6)*
15–29	0.9 (0.9, 1.0)	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*
30–64	0.5 (0.5, 0.5)*	0.4 (0.4, 0.4)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*
Wealth quintile				
Lowest wealth	ref	ref	ref	ref
Second lowest	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.9)*	1.0 (0.9, 1.1)	0.9 (0.7, 1.1)
Middle	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	1.0 (0.9, 1.2)	0.7 (0.6, 0.9)*
Second highest	0.4 (0.3, 0.4)*	0.4 (0.3, 0.4)*	1.0 (0.8, 1.2)	0.7 (0.6, 0.9)*
Wealthiest	0.2 (0.2, 0.2)*	0.2 (0.2, 0.2)*	1.0 (0.8, 1.3)	0.7 (0.5, 0.9)*
At least 1 ITN per 1.8 household members				
No	ref	ref	ref	ref
Yes	0.9 (0.9, 1.0)	0.9 (0.9, 1.0)	0.9 (0.8, 1.0)	0.9 (0.8, 1.1)
Place of residence				
Rural	ref	ref	ref	ref
Urban	0.7 (0.6, 0.7)*	0.7 (0.6, 0.7)*	1.3 (1.1, 1.6)	1.4 (1.2, 1.7)*

540 OR: odds ratio; ref: reference value; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval.

541 *Statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.001.

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548 **Table 3. Adjusted odds ratio estimates for IgG seropositivity to *P. falciparum* antigens compared to seronegativity considering**
 549 **demographic, socioeconomic, and behavioral risk factors: Nigeria, 2018**

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)				
	AMA1	CSP	GLURP0	LSA1	MSP1
Sex					
Female	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Male	1.1 (1.0, 1.2)*	1.0 (0.9, 1.0)	0.9 (0.9, 1.0)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.8)*	0.9 (0.9, 1.0)*
Age group in years					
<5	ref	ref	ref	ref	
5–9	3.0 (2.7, 3.2)*	2.0 (1.8, 2.2)*	2.8 (2.6, 3.0)*	1.9 (1.8, 2.1)*	2.3 (2.1, 2.5)*
10–14	5.6 (5.0, 6.1)*	4.4 (4.0, 4.8)*	6.1 (5.5, 6.6)*	3.1 (2.9, 3.4)*	2.8 (2.5, 3.1)*
15–29	20.1 (17.7, 22.8)*	12.5 (11.4, 13.7)*	11.0 (10.2, 11.9)*	4.8 (4.5, 5.2)*	6.9 (6.3, 7.5)*
30–64	37.5 (32.7, 43.0)*	31.0 (28.2, 34.0)*	15.1 (13.9, 16.3)*	5.5 (5.1, 6.0)*	11.5 (10.4, 12.8)*
Wealth quintile					
Lowest wealth	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Second lowest	0.6 (0.5, 0.7)*	0.7 (0.6, 0.8)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.9 (0.8, 1.0)
Middle	0.4 (0.4, 0.5)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.7 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.9)*
Second highest	0.3 (0.2, 0.3)*	0.5 (0.4, 0.5)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.7 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.7)*
Wealthiest	0.1 (0.1, 0.2)*	0.3 (0.3, 0.3)*	0.4 (0.3, 0.4)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.3 (0.3, 0.4)*
At least 1 ITN per 1.8 household members					
No	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Yes	1.1 (1.0, 1.3)	1.1 (1.0, 1.1)	1.2 (1.2, 1.3)*	1.1 (1.0, 1.1)*	1.1 (1.0, 1.3)*
Place of residence					
Rural	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Urban	0.4 (0.3, 0.4)*	0.5 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.7)*	0.7 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.5 (0.5, 0.6)*

550 OR: odds ratio; ref: reference; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval

551 *Statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.001.

552 **Figures**

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554

555 **Figure 1. Seropositivity by age for IgG against *P. falciparum* antigens AMA1, CSP, GLURP0,**
556 **LSA1, and MSP1 for persons <65 years: Nigeria, 2018.** Dots indicate the proportion seropositive while
557 error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for seropositivity in each age group. Fits of each catalytic
558 seroconversion model are represented by curves, while shaded areas are 95% credible intervals of model
559 predictions. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95% confidence intervals for IgG
560 against each antigen. All plots represent data from 87,344 biologically independent samples.

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Figure 2. IgG seropositivity by age for *P. falciparum* MSP1, AMA1, CSP, GLURP0, and LSA1 antigens by wealth quintile and urban/rural residence: Nigeria, 2018. Dots indicate the proportion seropositive while error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for each age group. Curves represent the fitting to the catalytic seroconversion model and shaded areas are 95% credible intervals. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95% confidence intervals. All plots represent data from 87,344 biologically independent samples.

574

575 **Figure 3. Exceedance probabilities for seroprevalence to short-term *P. falciparum* antigen markers**
 576 **and prevalence of active *P. falciparum* infection among children <15 years of age: Nigeria, 2018.**

577 Exceedance probabilities indicating elevated risk of (sero)prevalence to (A) CSP IgG, (B) GLURP0 IgG,
 578 (C) LSA1 IgG, and (D) HRP2 antigen are depicted for each of 694 local government areas (LGAs) of 774
 579 in Nigeria for which DBS data were collected and available for analysis. Probabilities are calculated
 580 based on (sero)prevalence estimates from R-INLA models that adjusted for mean participant age, altitude,
 581 aridity, population density, rainfall, temperature, and travel time to the nearest urban center. Darker
 582 purple shading indicates higher probability of exceeding the indicated threshold, while white shading
 583 indicates uncertainty of exceedance; darker green shading indicates lower probability of exceeding a
 584 given threshold. LGAs in grey had no data either collected or available for analysis.

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587 **Figure 4. Mean estimated coefficients of covariates with 95% credible intervals for (sero)prevalence**
588 **to CSP, GLURP0, LSA1, and HRP2 at the local government area level among children <15 years:**
589 **Nigeria, 2018.** All covariates have been mean-centered and standardized. Dots represent mean estimated
590 beta coefficients for covariates used in R-INLA models and bars are the coefficients' 95% credible
591 intervals. A vertical line at 0.0 represents a null effect; bars that do not cross this line indicate the
592 corresponding covariate had a statistically significant effect on seroprevalence to a given target at an
593 alpha level of 0.05.

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602 **Supplementary Material**

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604 **Figures**

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606 **Fig. S1. Map of Nigeria displaying the local government areas (LGAs) where DBS samples were**
607 **collected during the NAHS among children <15 years. LGAs in grey ($n = 30$) did not have such data**
608 **collected. The total number of LGAs in Nigeria is 774.**

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610 **Fig. S2. Spearman's rho coefficients for correlations among continuous IgG levels against *P.***

611 ***falciparum* antigens for persons <65 years: Nigeria, 2018.**

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615 **Fig. S3. Seropositivity by age for IgG against AMA1, CSP, GLURP0, LSA1, and MSP1 among**

616 **children <15 years: Nigeria, 2018.** Dots indicate the proportion seropositive while error bars represent

617 95% confidence intervals for seropositivity in each age group. Fits of each catalytic seroconversion model

618 are represented by curves. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95% confidence

619 intervals for IgG against each antigen. All plots represent data from 30,073 biologically independent

620 samples.

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625 **Fig. S4. Seropositivity by age for IgG against AMA1, CSP, GLURP0, LSA1, and MSP1 among**

626 **children <15 years by wealth quintile: Nigeria, 2018.** Dots indicate the proportion seropositive while

627 error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for seropositivity in each age group. Fits of each catalytic

628 seroconversion model are represented by curves, while shaded areas are 95% credible intervals of model

629 predictions. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95% confidence intervals for IgG

630 against each antigen for each quintile of household wealth. All plots represent data from 30,073

631 biologically independent samples.

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639 **Fig. S5. Seropositivity by age for IgG against AMA1, CSP, GLURP0, LSA1, and MSP1 among**

640 **children <15 years by urban versus rural residence: Nigeria, 2018.** Dots indicate the proportion

641 seropositive while error bars represent 95% confidence intervals for seropositivity in each age group. Fits

642 of each catalytic seroconversion model are represented by curves, while shaded areas are 95% credible

643 intervals of model predictions. Text in all plots provide the seroconversion rate (SCR) with 95%

644 confidence intervals for IgG against each antigen for each quintile of household wealth. All plots

645 represent data from 30,073 biologically independent samples.

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657 **Fig. S7. Estimated seroprevalence to short-term *P. falciparum* antigen markers and prevalence of**

658 **active *P. falciparum* infection among children <15 years of age: Nigeria, 2018. (Sero)prevalence**

659 estimates for (A) CSP, (B) GLURP0, (C) LSA1, and (D) HRP2 are depicted for each of 694 local

660 government areas (LGAs) of 774 in Nigeria for which DBS data were collected and available for analysis.

661 Estimates are from R-INLA models that adjusted for mean participant age, altitude, aridity, population

662 density, rainfall, temperature, and travel time to the nearest urban center. Darker orange shading indicates

663 higher (sero)prevalence, while paler shades of orange indicate lower (sero)prevalence. LGAs in grey had

664 no data either collected or available for analysis. LGA boundaries are outlined, and a scale bar and north

665 arrow are included.

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668 **Tables**

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670 **Table S1. Remote sensing data units, resolutions, and sources.**

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Variable	Unit	Spatial Resolution	Temporal Resolution	Source
Altitude	m	30 arc-seconds	N/A	CGIAR SRTM ¹
Aridity	index	30 arc-seconds	1970–2000 period	CGIAR CSI ²
Population density	population/100 m ²	3 arc-seconds	1 year	WorldPop ³
Rainfall	mm	0.05 x 0.05 degree	1 dekad	CHIRPS ⁴
Temperature	°C	0.05 decimal degrees	1 month	Accessible by figshare ⁵
Travel time to urban center	minutes	1 km	N/A	Weiss et al., 2018 ⁶

672 ¹<https://bigdata.cgiar.org/srtm-90m-digital-elevation-database/>

673 ²<https://cgiarcsi.community/2019/01/24/global-aridity-index-and-potential-evapotranspiration-climate-database-v3/>

674 ³<https://www.worldpop.org/geodata/listing?id=77>

675 ⁴https://data.chc.ucsb.edu/products/CHIRPS-2.0/global_monthly/tifs/

676 ⁵<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.4081802.v1>

677 ⁶Weiss, D. J., et al. (2018). "A global map of travel time to cities to assess inequalities in accessibility in 2015."

678 *Nature* 553(7688): 333-336

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684 **Table S2. Median and interquartile range of aggregated local government area-level variables used**
 685 **in geospatial modeling of *P. falciparum* outcomes among children <15 years: Nigeria 2018*.**

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Variable	Median (IQR)
Age (years)	7 (6–8)
Altitude (m)	260 (100–415)
Aridity (index)	0.08 (0.04–0.12)
Population Density (population/100 m ²)	12 (9–18)
Rainfall (mm)	115 (83–167)
Temperature (°C)	30.5 (29.1–33.2)
Travel time to urban center (minutes)	31 (14–54)

687 *Data are from 694 out of 742 local government areas (LGAs) for which DBS samples among children <15 years of
 688 age were collected in NAHIS, with a median sample size of 36 children per LGA (IQR: 21–57).
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701 **Table S3. Median and interquartile range of (sero)prevalence aggregated to the local government**
 702 **area level for *P. falciparum* outcomes assessed in geospatial modeling among children <15 years:**
 703 **Nigeria 2018*.**

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Outcome	Median (IQR)
CSP seroprevalence	0.25 (0.14–0.38)
GLURP0 seroprevalence	0.36 (0.25–0.47)
LSA1 seroprevalence	0.27 (0.18–0.38)
HRP2 prevalence	0.47 (0.27–0.61)

705 *Data are from 694 out of 742 local government areas (LGAs) for which DBS samples among children <15 years of
 706 age were collected in NAHIS, with a median sample size of 36 children per LGA (IQR: 21–57).
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721 **Table S4. Crude odds ratio estimates for *P. falciparum* infection by HRP2 and *P. falciparum* density**
722 **by PfLDH compared to no infection or no/low density considering demographic, socioeconomic,**
723 **and behavioral risk factors: Nigeria, 2018.**

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Variable	HRP2 Crude OR (95% CI) Positive vs. Negative	PfLDH Crude OR (95% CI)		
		Positive vs. Negative	Moderate Positive vs. Low Positive	High Positive vs. Low Positive
Sex				
Female	ref	ref	ref	ref
Male	1.4 (1.3, 1.4)*	1.4 (1.3, 1.4)*	0.9 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.9 (0.8, 0.9)*
Age group in years				
<5	ref	ref	ref	ref
5–9	1.6 (1.5, 1.8)*	1.7 (1.6, 1.8)*	1.1 (0.9, 1.4)	0.9 (0.7, 1.1)
10–14	1.4 (1.3, 1.5)*	1.4 (1.3, 1.5)*	0.8 (0.7, 1.0)	0.4 (0.4, 0.6)*
15–30	0.9 (0.8, 1.0)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*
30–64	0.5 (0.5, 0.5)*	0.4 (0.4, 0.5)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)*
Wealth quintile				
Lowest wealth	ref	ref	ref	ref
Second lowest	0.8 (0.7, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	1.0 (0.9, 1.1)	0.8 (0.7, 1.0)*
Middle	0.5 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.5 (0.5, 0.6)*	1.0 (0.9, 1.1)	0.7 (0.6, 0.8)*
Second highest	0.3 (0.3, 0.3)*	0.3 (0.3, 0.4)*	1.1 (0.9, 1.2)	0.8 (0.6, 0.9)*
Wealthiest	0.2 (0.1, 0.2)*	0.2 (0.1, 0.2)*	1.0 (0.8, 1.2)	0.6 (0.5, 0.8)*
At least 1 ITN per 1.8 household members				
No	ref	ref	ref	ref
Yes	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.7 (0.6, 0.7)*	0.6 (0.6, 0.7)*
Place of residence				
Rural	ref	ref	ref	ref
Urban	0.4 (0.4, 0.4)*	0.4 (0.4, 0.5)*	1.2 (1.1, 1.4)*	1.1 (0.9, 1.2)

725 OR: odds ratio; ref: reference; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval

726 *Statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.001.

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732 **Table S5. Crude odds ratio estimates for IgG seropositivity to *P. falciparum* antigens compared to seronegativity considering**
 733 **demographic, socioeconomic, and behavioral risk factors: Nigeria, 2018.**

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Crude OR (95% CI)					
Variable	AMA1	CSP	GLURP0	LSA1	MSP1
Sex					
Female	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Male	0.9 (0.9, 1.0)	0.9 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.9 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*
Age group in years					
<5		ref	ref	ref	
5–9	2.5 (2.3, 2.7)*	2.0 (1.8, 2.1)*	2.7 (2.5, 2.9)*	1.9 (1.8, 2.1)*	2.2 (2.0, 2.4)*
10–14	3.8 (3.5, 4.2)*	3.8 (3.4, 4.1)*	5.4 (4.9, 5.8)*	3.0 (2.7, 3.3)*	2.5 (2.2, 2.7)*
15–30	13.9 (12.2, 15.9)*	10.7 (9.8, 11.7)*	10.3 (9.4, 11.1)*	4.9 (4.5, 5.3)*	6.5 (6.0, 7.1)*
30–64	24.4 (21.2, 28.0)*	24.3 (22.0, 26.8)*	13.6 (12.5, 14.8)*	5.5 (5.1, 5.9)*	10.5 (9.4, 11.6)*
Wealth quintile					
Lowest wealth	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Second lowest	0.6 (0.6, 0.7)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.9 (0.8, 1.0)
Middle	0.4 (0.4, 0.5)*	0.6 (0.6, 0.7)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.8)*	0.8 (0.8, 0.9)*	0.8 (0.7, 0.9)*
Second highest	0.2 (0.2, 0.3)*	0.5 (0.4, 0.5)*	0.6 (0.5, 0.6)*	0.7 (0.6, 0.7)*	0.5 (0.4, 0.5)*
Wealthiest	0.1 (0.1, 0.1)*	0.3 (0.3, 0.3)*	0.4 (0.3, 0.4)*	0.5 (0.5, 0.5)*	0.2 (0.2, 0.3)*
At least 1 ITN per 1.8 household members					
No	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Yes	1.4 (1.3, 1.6)*	1.3 (1.3, 1.4)*	1.4 (1.3, 1.5)*	1.2 (1.2, 1.3)*	1.4 (1.3, 1.5)*
Place of residence					
Rural	ref	ref	ref	ref	ref
Urban	0.2 (0.2, 0.3)*	0.4 (0.4, 0.4)*	0.5 (0.4, 0.5)*	0.6 (0.6, 0.6)*	0.4 (0.3, 0.4)*

735 OR: odds ratio; ref: reference; 95% CI: 95% confidence interval

736 *Statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.001.

737

738 **Table S6. Mean estimated coefficients of covariates with 95% credible intervals for**
739 **(sero)prevalence to CSP, GLURP0, LSA1, and HRP2 at the local government area level among**
740 **children <15 years: Nigeria, 2018.**

741

Variable	CSP	GLURP0	LSA1	HRP2
Age	0.13 (0.07, 0.19)*	0.17 (0.12, 0.22)*	0.09 (0.04, 0.15)*	0.00 (-0.06, 0.06)
Altitude	-0.05 (-0.20, 0.10)	-0.17 (-0.29, -0.04)*	-0.07 (-0.19, 0.04)	-0.09 (-0.24, 0.06)
Aridity	0.38 (-0.10, 0.87)	0.23 (-0.18, 0.65)	0.19 (-0.20, 0.58)	0.36 (-0.14, 0.86)
Population Density	-0.44 (-0.54, -0.35)*	-0.34 (-0.41, -0.28)*	-0.36 (-0.43, -0.29)*	-0.44 (-0.53, -0.36)*
Rainfall	-0.15 (-0.52, 0.22)	-0.25 (-0.55, 0.06)	-0.29 (-0.59, 0.01)	-0.31 (-0.68, 0.07)
Temperature	0.13 (-0.12, 0.38)	0.07 (-0.14, 0.28)	0.03 (-0.16, 0.22)	0.00 (-0.26, 0.25)
Travel Time to Urban Center	0.08 (0.01, 0.15)*	0.05 (-0.02, 0.11)	0.03 (-0.04, 0.09)	0.09 (0.02, 0.17)*

742 All covariates have been mean-centered and standardized.

743 *Statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

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756 **Table S7. Spearman’s rank correlations, ρ , and 95% confidence intervals comparing**
 757 **seroprevalence among short-term *P. falciparum* antigens by local government area in Nigeria,**
 758 **2018*.**
 759

<u>Comparison</u>	<u>ρ (95% CI)</u>
CSP vs. LSA1	0.76 (0.73–0.79)
CSP vs. GLURP0	0.76 (0.73–0.79)
LSA1 vs. GLURP0	0.80 (0.77–0.83)

760 *Data are from 694 out of 742 local government areas (LGAs) for which DBS samples among children <15 years of
 761 age were collected in NAHIS, with a median sample size of 36 children per LGA (IQR: 21–57).
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794 **Supplemental Methods**

795 *Multiplex bead-based antigen detection assay*

796 At the NRL, a 6-mm punch (approximately 10 μ L of whole blood) was taken from each DBS
797 sample for rehydration and the blood was eluted to a 1:40 concentration in blocking buffer (Buffer B:
798 phosphate buffered saline (PBS) pH 7.2, 0.5% bovine serum albumin (BSA), 0.05% Tween 20, 0.02%
799 sodium azide, 0.5% polyvinyl alcohol, 0.8% polyvinylpyrrolidone, and 3 μ g/mL *Escherichia coli*
800 extract).¹⁶ Blood elutions were stored at 4°C until testing. As described previously, samples were assayed
801 in singlet at 1:40 whole blood dilution for HRP2 and *P. falciparum* LDH (PfLDH).¹⁷ Assay plates were
802 read on MAGPIX™ instruments (Luminex Corporation, Austin, TX), and, with a target of at least 50
803 beads per region, the median fluorescence intensity (MFI) was generated for each analyte by Luminex
804 xPonent software version 4.2 (Luminex Corporation). For each assay plate, the MFI signal for the sample
805 dilution buffer (buffer background) was subtracted from each target's MFI signal to provide an MFI
806 minus background (MFI-bg) assay signal for analysis.

807 Variations from plate to plate were accounted for with assessment of controls on each plate,
808 inclusive of antigen-negative blood (at 1:40 dilution) and a four-point titration curve of a recombinant
809 antigen-positive pool. As described previously, assay plates “failed” if the negative controls displayed a
810 positive signal or if the positive controls for both PfLDH and HRP2 were two standard deviations outside
811 of the cumulative moving average of the MFI-bg signal for the assay plates.¹⁷ Plates that failed were re-
812 run to obtain valid data.

813

814 *Multiplex bead-based IgG detection assay*

815 The multiplex bead-based assay (MBA) to detect IgG was performed as described previously and
816 included targets for various infectious and vaccine-preventable diseases.¹⁶ Assay plates were run using the
817 same machines and software as the antigen detection assay described above. From the same DBS elution
818 used above, assays were run in singlet with a final serum dilution of approximately 1:400. For the current
819 study, analysis was restricted to the *Schistosoma japonicum* glutathione-S-transferase (GST) internal

820 control antigen as well as the following *Plasmodium falciparum* antigens: apical membrane antigen 1
821 (AMA1), circumsporozoite surface protein (CSP), glutamate-rich protein R0 (GLURP0), liver-stage
822 antigen 1 (LSA1), and the 19kDa fragment of the merozoite surface protein 1 molecule (MSP1).
823 Variations by plate were accounted for with assessment of controls on each assay plate, with a pass-fail
824 structure like that described above. Assay controls for the IgG detection assay included a 1:400 dilution of
825 a negative-control sera pool from U.S. residents without malaria exposure and a positive-control pool of
826 residents from various *P. falciparum* transmission settings. As described previously, Levey-Jennings
827 charts were used to track deviations in assay signals over time for the positive controls.¹⁸ An assay plate
828 “failed” if negative controls showed a positive signal or if positive controls were two standard deviations
829 outside of the cumulative moving average.
830